

Science Investigator-Led Global Processing for the MODIS instrument

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I. INTRODUCTION

The Moderate Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS) instrument produces over 700GB/day of global science products from science algorithms developed by over 20 principal investigators from the land, oceans, and atmosphere disciplines. In 1999, the MODIS Science Team assumed the responsibility for the operational production of MODIS products. This was a fundamental shift from the previous model in which 3 processing and data archive centers, developed, maintained and operated by the EOS Science Data and Information System Project (ESDIS), were planned to have responsibility for production of the MODIS products. Shifting responsibility for operational processing to the MODIS science team: reduced the cost of producing the data products, shortened the time required to get software changes into production by weeks and gave scientists better control of production priorities.

II. SCIENTISTS' ROLES IN DEVELOPING MODAPS

A key advantage that arose from producing MODIS science products in the MODIS Adaptive Processing System (MODAPS) has been the close interaction between MODIS scientists and software developers under the terms of a PI Processing paradigm. During builds of the production system, MODIS science team members have been instrumental in developing and refining requirements for the system, and reviewing progress in system design and implementation.

Scientists also work with the development team to reach a balance between complex production rules for determining when jobs are eligible to run in the system which might optimize the quality of an individual product and simpler production rules that save system resources. In general once operational processing is underway, simple production rules that limited the number of alternate inputs used by science software are usually preferred by scientists since these rules maintain consistency in how products are generated over time.

Scientists have also been instrumental in refining the interface for ordering products and the reports used to detect errors in

production or track the volume of products shipped to archive centers and Science Team computing facilities. In particular, graphical charts on the MODAPS production Web page [1], which show the status of individual products and allow a user to drill down to the actual products and their production histories, have been invaluable in rapidly identifying and debugging problems in production. A prototype of these charts was created by a member of the MODIS land team and implemented with minor modifications for all MODIS products by the software development team.

With the development of the MODAPS system under the MODIS science team, we have been able to both tap the resources of the science team for help and get science team buy-in for new architectures that increase resources for production and reduce operation costs. Porting MODIS science software to Intel Pentium 3 processors under Linux is an example of an activity which was approved by the science team and enabled the MODIS team to significantly increase the processing power of MODAPS at a relatively low cost.

III. SCIENTISTS' ROLES IN DAILY PRODUCTION

Every weekday, software leads from the MODIS science team and data support team meet with the operations and development leads from MODAPS. At the meeting, production plans for the day are reviewed, upcoming science software changes are identified, the status of science software integration and test activities and MODAPS software development is presented, new requests for MODAPS enhancements or bug fixes are identified, and priorities are set for all operations and development activities. Decisions to delay production of a given group of products are also made at the morning meeting. If a defect has been identified in a product or if a new version of software will be delivered shortly, a discipline may request a production delay for the product and other products which use it as input.

Each MODIS science discipline also holds a weekly meeting where science software, quality assurance and validation activities are discussed. The software integration lead from the data support team attends the meeting to discuss progress or issues in science software integration or problems uncovered in operations. This meeting, which includes most

of the science software developers, provides an important channel for communicating plans for the delivery of improvements to science software and reviewing problems in the MODAP that may impact the science team activities.

At a weekly PI processing team meeting, the MODIS Science Team Leader and representatives from each science discipline meet with the data support team leader and operations managers from the GES(Goddard Earth Sciences) DAAC and MODAPS to set priorities and develop schedules for long term activities like major reprocessing campaigns. This meeting also covers status of weekly production and any special requests for processing to support field campaigns or outreach activities.

IV. MODIS SOFTWARE INTEGRATION

MODIS science algorithms coded in C, Fortran 77 and Fortran 90 and toolkits and scripts written in Perl comprise over 650,000 lines of executable code. In the year following the launch of EOS-Terra, there were over 500 separate changes to science software delivered by the MODIS science team for integration into the production system. Efficient processes for configuration management, integration and testing were key to the rapid delivery of science software improvements into the production system.

Figure 1 illustrates the cycle that science software follows from its delivery by a scientist to its running in the production system and subsequent identification of defects in the product by quality assurance teams. This figure focuses on the process flow for the science software installed on the MODAPS system. Additionally, the data support team also processes software supplied to the DAAC, which generates Level 1 (L1) products used as input to the MODAPS system.

Once a new version of science software has been delivered, a

Fig. 1 MODIS Science Software Update Process

Science Software Transfer Group (SSTG) adds a Perl script and I/O toolkit routines needed to run it in the production system. The production capable software is referred to as a Product Generation Executive (PGE). The MODIS instrument on the Terra spacecraft presently utilizes 52 separate PGEs. SSTG compiles the software and runs a unit test on MODAPS with the input provided by the developer. If the unit test yields comparable results to the output files provided by the developer then the software is delivered to the configuration manager (CM), who imports it into the ClearCase configuration management system.

Before the new version of the software is put into production, it has to pass a larger test in the Integration and Test (I&T) Group with selected granules or tiles, which better simulates production and is designed to catch problems identified in this or related PGEs. In this test, the PGE is combined with all the other PGEs in its production recipe. Additionally if several key PGEs in a discipline are being changed, a full end to end test for that discipline will be conducted to assess the effects of software changes on the entire suite of products. In reviewing the tests, the test team verifies that the PGE ran to completion without errors and produced products of the correct size with correct metadata. The products may also be examined by the science team prior to approving the installation of the revised science software into the production system. If problems are found at this stage the PGE is returned to the SSTG team which either fixes the defect or returns the PGE to the developer with an explanation of the problem.

Once in production the output of all products are evaluated by quality assurance teams from each science discipline (oceans, land and atmosphere) which post product defects on the MODIS Web page [1, 2, 3]. At any point in this lifecycle a new version of the science software may be sent in by the developer either in response to a defect identified by one of the tests or quality assurance processes or because the new version will improve the quality of the science product.

The streamlined process of integration and testing has enabled the support team to integrate and test approximately 2 science software changes per working day of which 1 on average passed all tests and was promoted into production as shown in Table 1. This table reflects Terra software changes only and the actual productivity of SSTG, CM, and the I&T Group has been approximately 30% higher including PGEs for the MODAPS development systems and MODIS PGEs for the planned Aqua mission.

The time it takes for a PGE change to make it through the test process is a function of: the workload of the test team, the priority and complexity of the PGE change and whether or not the PGE can wait for other PGEs that are in the same or related processing threads. With 4 testers responsible for

testing changes to the MODAPS production system and the MODIS science PGEs, it has been important to test related PGE changes together in order to make efficient use of the support resources. Working closely with the MODIS science team to understand the relative priority of getting a particular PGE change into production and when future changes to related PGEs might be delivered, has allowed MODIS to better optimize the work of the test team.

- [2] Roy, David P. et. al, "The MODIS Land Product Quality Assessment Approach", submitted to Remote Sensing of Environment.
- [3] Justice, C.O. et al, "The Moderate Resolution Imaging Spectroradiometer (MODIS): Land remote sensing for global change research", IEEE Transactions on Geoscience and Remote Sensing, Vol. 36: pp. 1228-1249.

	PASSED SSTG UNIT TEST	PASSED I&T TEST	INSTALLED IN MODAPS OPERATIONS
Mar-00	29	23	26
Apr-00	20	17	17
May-00	39	33	25
Jun-00	36	18	18
Jul-00	30	18	17
Aug-00	24	12	20
Sep-00	25	20	20
Oct-00	47	29	36
Nov-00	27	22	27
Dec-00	19	16	22
Jan-01	34	17	16
Feb-01	22	24	7
Total	352	249	251

Table 1 Number of MODIS PGE changes passing a step of the integration and test process.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Taking on the responsibility for the operational production of MODIS science products has enabled the MODIS Science Team and their data support team to respond to the former's requirements and the latter's constraints in a rapid manner, streamline the process of getting science software into production, maximize quality of products, increase resources available for production and obtain resources for improved quality assurance of products. When MODIS product volume reaches nearly 8TB/day in 2003, further improvements in the process of science software testing will be needed to catch errors before they reach production. Additional automated quality assurance software will also be needed to flag problems in the large volume of data products generated daily.

REFERENCES

- [1] Information about product quality is available at MODIS home page at: <http://ftpwww.gsfc.nasa.gov/MODIS>